

Pathology of Salt Poisoning In Poultry

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Abstract

Sodium poisoning, resulting from excessive intake of sodium ions, has been intermittently reported in confinement-reared poultry and can lead to considerable economic losses in affected flocks. Acute or direct salt poisoning typically occurs due to excessive consumption of salt through feed and/or drinking water, with clinical signs usually appearing within 1–2 days of high sodium intake. The availability and intake of water play a crucial role in the pathophysiology of sodium toxicosis. Delayed or indirect Salt poisoning often arises when excessive sodium intake is combined with restricted water availability, a common predisposing factor. In such cases, clinical signs generally become evident within 4–7 days following water deprivation.

Key Words: Diagnosis, Pathology, Poultry, Salt Poisoning, Treatment

INTRODUCTION:

Salt intoxication may occur in any animal species and studies have been carried out to determine the salt toxic levels in chickens, turkeys, ducks and pigeons. During the last 40-50 years the poultry industry has developed from a primitive rural farming setup to mass production industry with computerized controlled environmental conditions. The advance in poultry farming and production involved vast technological developments of the feed mills, feed production and quality control systems. Salt (Sodium chloride) is one of the major components of feed for the normal maintenance of biological processes. Addition of sodium chloride to the rations of broilers is essential for optimum growth. The ideal content of sodium chloride in the ration of chicks is said to be 1200 mg/kg basal ration. But excessive doses of salt can cause toxic effects in chickens. Young chicks are most susceptible due to indiscriminate feeding behaviour, poor sense of taste, low plasma proteins in chicks and decreased glomerular filtration area in the kidneys of chicks compared to mammals. Salt intoxication reports are very rare and salt intoxication presents the same clinical and

pathological findings of other sodium related compounds such as sodium iodide, sodium bicarbonate. Despite all these technological amenities, a relatively extensive salt/sodium intoxication incident involving several broiler farms (Biester and Schwarte, 1967; Cantile and Youssef, 2016).

SOURCES OF POISONING:

Feeds containing high quantities of common salts, accidental over ingestion of common salts causes poisoning. The occurrences of poisoning may be due to change from low salt ration to high salt ration, low Vitamin-E and Sulphur containing amino acids. Toxicity may be reduced by providing sufficient quantity of water immediately after ingestion of large salts. The surplus sodium ions are excreted primarily by the kidneys and little by skin and alimentary tract. Toxic dose of salts is 0.25-2 % of the diet in case of poultry when water supply is restricted, however when drinking water is freely available, toxic dose is 5-10% (Dewar et al., 1972; Dewar, 1973).

MECHANISM OF ACTION:

Sodium ions and water balance are mainly disturbed due to excess intake of salts. Excess of sodium ions in gastrointestinal tract causes mild irritation and secretion of water into the lumen of intestine and thus diarrhoea further causes dehydration. Absorption of Na⁺ results in hypertonicity of blood and hypernatremia, shrinkage of kidney tubules, deposition of sodium crystals in the tubules, anuria, uremia etc. following transient polyuria due to initial excretion of Na⁺ in the urine (Harms, 1991).

CLINICAL SIGNS:

Exhibition of nervous symptoms started by the end of second week and continued till sixth week. There was increased thirst, excessive oral secretion, dull, depressed and restlessness. Increased fluid discharge from beak, weakness, wet faeces and limb paralysis are common in poultry. Sudden and sharp increase in mortality begins and healthy chicks lying on their backs and pedalling with their feet (Horowitz and Latimer, 2010).

Chicks also show severe depression and apathy with some clinical signs of brain involvement such as incoordination and head Opisthotonus. Sometimes birds showed severe respiratory distress, similar to that observed in post vaccinal respiratory reactions or infectious bronchitis. Presence of subcutaneous edema mainly in young one and the shank also swollen due to edema. There is rapid reduction in egg production and the litters become wet due to this toxicity.

Chicks laying on their backs with spread legs due to ascites and anasarca	Chick gasping showing respiratory distress
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Severity of clinical signs are mostly observed in the youngest birds reaching about 5% mortality per day with thousands of chicks falling

on their backs with severe difficulty in breathing (Klasing, 2013).

POST MORTEM CHANGES:

Gross examination mainly includes severe ascites, hydro-pericardium and congestion of heart, liver, kidney and intestine. Deposition of uric acid in kidneys, ureters and droppings of mature birds. The main lesions are oedematous swelling of testes with severe congestion and appearance of testis is transparent. There is presence of showing congestion in the brain. Muscles become pale and watery (Peckam, 1967; Fulton, 2020).

HISTOPATHOLOGICAL CHANGES:

Microscopically, section of testes showed severe, dilatation as well as rupture of seminiferous tubules, flattening of epithelium and thickening of interstitial tissue with mononuclear cell infiltration. Section of brain revealed severe vascular congestion. Section of liver and kidneys showed degenerative changes particularly around blood vessels with severe vascular congestion (Scrivner, 1946; Horowitz and Latimer, 2010).

Chicks with swollen oedematous shanks	Subcutaneous oedema
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Oedematous swelling of testes with severe congestion and testes appeared transparent	Congestion and oedematous swelling of kidneys
Severe vascular congestion	Severe, dilatation as well as rupture of seminiferous tubules, flattening of epithelium.

DIAGNOSIS:

- ❖ History of salt ingestion.
- ❖ Clinical signs of poisoning including excessive thirst.
- ❖ Post-mortem lesions.
- ❖ Circumstantial evidences of relatively restricted water or salt supply.
- ❖ Laboratory investigations indicating plasma sodium levels of exceeding the normal value.

TREATMENT:

- ❖ Remove the toxic feed or water.
- ❖ Salt free fresh water be made available
- ❖ Gastrointestinal tract sedatives
- ❖ Sedatives to counter the CNS stimulation

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